

Pseudohalogenodephenylation of Ph_3SnCl and Dephenylation of Ph_2SnCl_2

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HALOGENODEPHENYLATION reactions of Ph_3SnX ($\text{X}=\text{NCO}$, NCS and N_3) with ICl and/or IBr have been reported by us¹. In the present investigation, we report the pseudohalogenodephenylation reactions of Ph_3SnCl with IX ($\text{X}=\text{NCO}$, NCS and N_3) (generated *in situ*) which give $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{X})\text{Cl}$, and the dephenylation reactions of Ph_2SnCl_2 with IX which yield SnCl_2I_2 and SnClI .

Dephenylation of one phenyl group from Ph_3SnCl in comparison to the dephenylation of both the phenyl groups from Ph_2SnCl_2 is rationalised in terms of the presence of more electron-withdrawing (Cl) groups in the latter in comparison to the former.

Experimental

Ph_2SnCl_2 was prepared by the reported method². Ph_3SnCl , Bu_3SnCl , ICl (E. Merck) and NaX ($\text{X}=\text{NCO}$, NCS and N_3) (B.D.H.) were used. Cl, I were estimated volumetrically by Volhard's method³. All the reactions were carried out under nitrogen atmosphere. The physicochemical measurements were done as before¹.

Iodine pseudohalides, IX ($\text{X}=\text{NCO}$, NCS and N_3) were generated *in situ* and a typical preparation of INCO is as follows. To a stirred slurry of NaNCO (0.5058 g, 7.78 mmol) in acetonitrile (~10 ml) in a methanol-ice cold bath (-10°) was added slowly a solution of ICl (1.2645 g, 7.78 mmol) in the same solvent (~10 ml) over a period of 10–20 min and the mixture was stirred further for 5–10 min. It was then filtered to remove NaCl . To the solution chloroform (~50 ml) was added. Although INCO has never been isolated from the solution, its presence is inferred⁴. Similarly INCS and IN_3 were generated *in situ* and used as such.

Reactions of Ph_3SnCl with IX in 1 : 1 molar ratio and those of Ph_2SnCl_2 with IX in 1 : 2 molar ratio were performed as under :

Reaction of Ph_3SnCl with INCO (1 : 1): A solution of Ph_3SnCl (3.0 g, 7.78 mmol) in CHCl_3 (~25 ml) was added dropwise with vigorous stirring to the above dark-red solution of INCO (1.3151 g, 7.78 mmol) at ambient temperature. It was immediately followed by decolourisation. After complete addition, the mixture was refluxed for 2 h and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to ~10 ml by distilling off the excess of solvent. It was then distilled at 10 mm/Hg to give PhI (0.98 g, 61.7%). The residue was crystallised by addition of solvent ether to obtain light yellow solid, which was washed with solvent ether, dried at $30^\circ/10$ mm

Hg and identified as $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCO})\text{Cl}$ (0.40 g, 14.66%), m.p. 180° .

Reaction of Ph_3SnCl with INCS (1 : 1) : Under similar experimental conditions and by the aforesaid method, Ph_3SnCl (3.0 g, 7.78 mmol) with INCS (1.4396 g, 7.78 mmol) gave PhI (1.04 g, 65.5%) and crystallisation of the residue from solvent ether yielded $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{NCS})\text{Cl}$ (0.40 g, 14%), m.p. 162° .

Reaction of Ph_3SnCl with IN_3 (1 : 1) : Similarly, reaction of Ph_3SnCl (3.0 g, 7.78 mmol) with IN_3 (1.3151 g, 7.78 mmol) yielded PhI (1.08 g, 68%) and crystallisation of the residue from solvent ether gave $\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{N}_3)\text{Cl}$ (0.52 g, 19.06%), m.p. 167° .

These diphenyltin mixed chloride pseudohalides [$\text{Ph}_2\text{Sn}(\text{X})\text{Cl}$] gave satisfactory elemental (C, H, N, Cl, Sn) analyses. Their ir spectra revealed characteristic absorptions associated with the phenyl rings at their usual positions : ν_{asym} and ν_{sym} absorptions associated with the NCO, NCS and N_3 at 2 235, 1 325 ; 2 085, 835 and 2 080, 1 330 cm^{-1} respectively, indicating the presence of N-bonded pseudohalide group. Their ^1H nmr spectra revealed two multiplets corresponding to *ortho*- and *meta*- and *para*-phenyl protons in the range 7.04–7.64⁶⁻⁷. These observations are in agreement with our earlier report¹.

Reaction of Ph_2SnCl_2 with INCO (1 : 2) : A solution of Ph_2SnCl_2 (6.0 g, 17.44 mmol) in CHCl_3 (~25 ml) was added dropwise with vigorous stirring to the above dark-red solution of INCO (5.8953 g, 34.88 mmol) at ambient temperature. It was then refluxed for 2 h and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to ~10 ml by distilling off the excess of solvent and then distilled at 10 mm/Hg to remove organic products. The resulting oily liquid was distilled at $150^\circ/10$ mm Hg and identified as SnCl_2I_2 (1.20 g, 15.49%) (Found : Cl, 15.82 ; I, 57.14 ; Sn, 26.75. SnCl_2I_2 calcd. for : Cl, 15.99 ; I, 57.20 ; Sn, 26.80%).

Reaction of Ph_2SnCl_2 with INCS (1 : 2) : The reaction of Ph_2SnCl_2 (6.0 g, 17.44 mmol) with INCS (6.4534 g, 34.88 mmol) gave red oily liquid of SnCl_2I_2 which was distilled at $150^\circ/10$ mm Hg ; (1.30 g, 16.78%) (Found : Cl, 15.92 ; I, 57.18 ; Sn, 26.67. SnCl_2I_2 calcd for : Cl, 15.99 ; I, 57.20 ; Sn, 26.80%).

Reaction of Ph_2SnCl_2 with IN_3 (1 : 2) : A solution of Ph_2SnCl_2 (3.0 g, 8.72 mmol) in CHCl_3 (~25 ml) was added dropwise with vigorous stirring to the above dark red solution of IN_3 (2.9476 g, 17.44 mmol) at ambient temperature. There was no colour change. It was refluxed for 2 h and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to ~10 ml by distilling off the excess of solvent and then distilled at 10 mm/Hg to remove other products. The residue was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. $40-60^\circ$) to obtain a light yellow product, SnClI (0.50 g, 20.36%) which did not melt upto 220° (Found : Cl, 12.52 ; I, 45.09 ; Sn, 42.24. SnClI calcd for : Cl, 12.61 ; I, 45.11 ; Sn, 42.27%).

The qualitative test of SnCl_2I_2 and SnClI indicated the absence of aromatic groups. Their ir spectra showed absence of bands corresponding to phenyl groups.

In the above cleavage reactions of Ph_2SnCl_2 , we have been able to characterise only SnCl_2I_2 or SnClI among other products. Reactions of Bu_3SnCl with IX (*in situ*) did not result in decolourisation, therefore they were not investigated further.

Results and Discussion

Although the yields of diphenyltin mixed chloride pseudohalides obtained by the pseudohalogenodephenylation of Ph_3SnCl are lower than those obtained previously¹, the route developed in the present investigation has an edge over the previous route for the synthesis of diphenyltin mixed chloride pseudohalides as Ph_3SnCl is commercially available. The dephenylation reactions of Ph_2SnCl_2 give inorganic tin salts not accessible easily and therefore, they provide an insight into potentiality for the use of organotin compounds in inorganic synthesis.

A possible rationale for the cleavage of one phenyl group from Ph_3SnCl and the cleavage of both the phenyl groups from Ph_2SnCl_2 , under similar experimental conditions, is given as follows. Ph_3SnCl has one electron-withdrawing (Cl) group whereas Ph_2SnCl_2 has two such groups. Therefore, because of more I-effect of Cl groups in Ph_2SnCl_2 , the π -electron density from the phenyl rings will be transferred more to the vacant *5d*-orbitals of tin, thus weakening Ph–Sn bond in Ph_2SnCl_2 in comparison to Ph–Sn bond in Ph_3SnCl . This causes facile cleavage of both the phenyl groups from Ph_2SnCl_2 whereas cleavage of only one phenyl group from Ph_3SnCl occurs. Such interactions between π -electron density of phenyl rings and vacant *5d*-orbitals of Sn atom in the presence of electron-withdrawing groups have previously been discussed through dipole moment⁸ and nmr data⁵.

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